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Prevalence of Frailty in Rural Areas of Lebanon

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the prevalence of the frailty syndrome and its association with demographic, economic, health, functional, nutritional, psychological and cognitive variables in rural areas of Lebanon. For this research, a cross-sectional study was conducted among 340 older people, aged 65 years and over, with an average age of 76.3 years. The relationships between stages of frailty and the variables of interest were made using the Pearson correlation and the Chi-square test. Frailty was prevalent among 48.2% of the subjects sampled and pre-frailty among 38.5%. Older females were found to be more likely to be frail and pre-frail. Frailty was associated with age, marital status, chronic disease, difficulty performing instrumental activities of daily living, basic activities of daily living, malnutrition and depression. The results of this study confirm that frailty is common in later life in rural areas of Lebanon and that interventions should focus on the development of strategies that are aimed at maximizing capacity, quality of life, and independence.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the past few decades, significant changes have been reported on the growth of the aging population throughout the world and the related negative impact on society. Driven by falling fertility rates and remarkable increases in life expectancy, population aging will continue to increase, and even accelerate in the decades ahead.⁽¹⁾ Among the 7.3 billion people worldwide in 2015, an estimated 8.5% were aged 65 and over. In this report, the number of elderly people is projected to increase by more than 60% until 2030, when there will be about 1 billion elderly people globally, equivalent to 12.0% of the total population. It is also estimated that, by 2050, people aged 65 years and over will comprise 16.7% of the total world population.⁽²⁾

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Using the proportion of elderly people as an indicator for aging, Europe historically has been the region with the most elderly population. However, Asia and Latin America are rapidly progressing through the demographic transition and population aging.⁽²⁾

Population aging in the Arab region follows a similar pattern to that taking place in the developing countries of Asia and Latin America.⁽³⁾ These demographic shifts have led to a remarkable modification in the age structure of their populations and a gradual increase in the proportion of older adults.⁽⁴⁾ This phenomenon was quoted by Palloni and colleagues as the “silent aging process”, which is the outcome of a rapid and concentrated decline in fertility and infant mortality, as well as a continuing increase in life expectancy.⁽⁵⁾

Compared to the rest of the Arab region, the population growth in Lebanon, which stands at less than 1% per year, is expected to be among the lowest in the first half of the 21st Century. The average population growth rate in the Arab region is expected to be 2.6% and 3.8% for those 65+ and 80+, respectively.⁽⁶⁾ It is estimated that, in Lebanon, approximately 10% of the population is currently aged 65+.⁽⁷⁾

1.1 Aging, Family and Chronic Diseases

With the number of elderly people growing in the Arab region, research revealed that there is a rapid increase in chronic, non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and disabilities among the older Arab populations.

Lozano, Rafael et al., based on a systematic analysis of 235 causes of death conducted for 20 age groups in 1990 and 2010, reported that cause-specific death rates combined to drive a broad shift from communicable, maternal, neonatal, and nutritional causes towards non-communicable diseases.⁽⁸⁾ Deaths from non-communicable diseases (NCDs) increased by 42% and, in 2010, accounted for two of every three deaths worldwide. Cardiovascular diseases, lung diseases, cancer and strokes are the leading causes of death for people aged 60 and over; however, with a few notable exceptions such as diabetes and chronic kidney disease. The drivers of mortality also vary considerably per region and level of economic development.⁽²⁾ Death and disability from non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are rapidly increasing in less developed countries and yielding worse outcomes than in more developed countries; some diseases that are leading to death in less developed countries are preventable or treatable in developed countries.⁽⁹⁾

The Health Profile of Older People in Lebanon revealed that non-communicable disease (NCDs) and degenerative diseases have become the leading causes of death and morbidity, taking over the position of communicable diseases. For instance, the national Pan Arab Project for Family Health (PAPFAM) survey, conducted by the Lebanese Central Administration of Statistics and the Ministry of Social Affairs in 2004 revealed that around three quarters of older persons in Lebanon reported at least one co-morbid medical condition and that one quarter perceived their health status as poor.⁽¹⁰⁾

For older people, having family is of particular importance.⁽¹¹⁾ As a social institution, the family unit is greatly valued and is assumed to be the main care provider for its elderly members.^(12,13) Sibai et al⁽¹⁴⁾ reported that increasing age and having a high number of children predicts a higher likelihood of co-residence with an adult child. Today, with there being significant changes in social status, such as women’s participation in the work force, industrialization and a decline in extended families,⁽³⁾ as well as high rates of emigration among youths, as a result of continuing political turmoil and economic uncertainties, the quantity and the quality of support for aging people is expected to decline in the years to come. Traditionally, ageing parents receive care from their children when they suffer debilitating

chronic conditions and diseases (e.g. significant sensory losses, disability, severe arthritis, Alzheimer, Parkinson), or when they are otherwise frail.

Further, current migration trends suggest that the rates of people living alone mirror the patterns that are observed in Western countries, with Lebanon having the highest prevalence rate of citizens living alone as compared to other Arab countries.⁽¹⁵⁾

It has been reported that 12% of adults 65+ in Lebanon live alone, and that older women (18%) are almost three times more likely to be living alone than older men (7%).⁽¹⁶⁾ Among those who live with others, the majority (89%) lives in their own homes.^(14,17)

1.2 Definition and Prediction of Frailty

The definition of frailty remains contested. In fact, the notion of frailty has gradually gained recognition and credibility in medical discourse through the identification that elderly people are at risk of death or of events affecting their autonomy and independence. The word frailty indicates a state of instability, with the risk of functional loss of capacity as a result of events that are sometimes quite minor.⁽¹⁸⁾

The classifications and definitions of frailty are numerous, but most of the literature considers frailty to be a condition in which a functional older person is impaired in some way and at increased risk of developing either disability, or even death, when exposed to physical or psychological stressors.^(19,20,21) A frail person has a reduced functional capacity, reserve, and resistance to stressors. Frailty is an accumulation of multiple deficits, which can be social, psychological or physiological,^(18,22,23) and is associated with a high prevalence of long-term adverse health-related outcomes,⁽²⁴⁾ such as a poor functional and cognitive status, falls, dependency, disability,⁽²⁵⁾ hospitalization,⁽²⁶⁾ institutionalization, and mortality.^(27,28)

Rockwood notes that: “Although we all know what we think frailty looks like, and manage ‘frail’ patients every day, a clear definition that meets rigorous criteria of content, construct and criterion validity, remains elusive”.⁽²⁹⁾ On December 7, 2012, a consensus conference convened in Orlando, Florida, USA, during which an operational definition of frailty was developed, as well as a framework for screening and treating frail persons.⁽³⁰⁾

Frailty also includes care dependency and co-morbidity. A study conducted by Fried et al. (2004) found co-morbidity in 57.7% of cases of frailty, and care dependency in 27.2% of cases, with neither being present in 21.5% of cases.⁽³¹⁾ Collard et al., in a systematic review, estimated that, among the general population, the prevalence of frailty ranges between 4% and 59.1%.⁽³²⁾ In addition, a large cross-sectional study that was conducted in 10 European countries, among randomly selected community-dwelling individuals aged 50 years and over, yielded that the proportion of frailty or pre-frailty was higher in southern Europe.⁽³³⁾ Estimates varied widely between high, middle and low income countries. Another study reported a prevalence of frailty in 39.2% of urban-dwelling Mexicans aged 70 and over.⁽³⁴⁾ Similarly, a prevalence of 37.7% was recorded in a Latin American and Caribbean study of people aged 60 and over.⁽³⁵⁾

However, a cross-sectional study conducted among community-dwelling people aged 55 years and over in Abu Dhabi, UAE, recorded a high prevalence of frailty (47%) among older age groups, especially among non-married women, people who had been admitted to hospital recently, those with co-morbid conditions, those on more than five medications, and those with a lower forced expiratory volume and mini-mental state examination score.⁽³⁶⁾

1.3 Assessing the Stages of Frailty

Other studies have been conducted to identify suitable instruments or tools for measuring stages of frailty. Most of the frail persons were being screened to determine which tools were the best for early detection of frailty, or for predicting patients' outcomes. While most studies used the Fried Phenotype method developed by Fried et al. in CHS study as a referral instrument to define frail older adults, other studies utilized similar tools to measure frailty.⁽²⁷⁾

Smets et al. compared four screening instruments for geriatric assessment (abbreviated Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment, Vulnerable Elders Survey-13, Groningen Frailty Indicator and Geriatric 8) to determine their sensitivity and specificity to identify and/or classify frailty; none of these screening instruments was deemed acceptable according to a minimum of 85% for both sensitivity and specificity.⁽³⁷⁾ A study conducted by Hoogendijk et al. concerning the accuracy of five (5) simple instruments of frailty assessment yielded that PRISMA-7 registered the best accuracy, but researchers suggested that there is still a need for further research about the predictive validity and clinical utility of such a simple instrument.⁽³⁸⁾ On the other hand, Romero-Ortuno et al. conducted a large-scale study in Europe that adopted a simple instrument based on the Fried Phenotype method (The SHARE Frailty instrument) and proved that it has sufficient construct and predictive validity.⁽³⁹⁾ Furthermore, Bouillon et al., in an overview concerning the measurement of frailty, noted that: "Although there are numerous frailty scales currently in use, their reliability and validity have rarely been examined. The most evaluated and frequently used measure is the Phenotype of Frailty."⁽⁴⁰⁾

The Fried Phenotype method identifies frailty by the presence of three or more of the following components: weight loss, weakness, poor endurance and energy or exhaustion, slowness and low physical activity. A critical mass of characteristics defined as three or more present for an individual was sufficient for the person to be considered frail. Persons with none of these characteristics were considered as robust, whereas those with one or two characteristics were hypothesized to be in an intermediate, possibly pre-frail, clinical stage.⁽²⁷⁾

As regards the assessment of the prevalence of frailty and its association with selected independent variables, stages of frailty vary markedly from one individual to another and appear to be reversible, although only a small proportion of frail individuals will return spontaneously to full robustness.^(41,42) Cesari et al. reported that interventions that are aimed at increasing physical activity have been shown to be effective, especially in individuals at higher risk of disability. Interventions that are aimed at improving nutrition may also be beneficial, but evidence for this is limited.^(43,44)

1.4 Rural and Urban Areas

Indeed, several studies have reported that there are health disparities between people living in urban areas and those living in rural areas. Those living in rural areas are older, poorer, suffer from more severe health conditions, and there are fewer physicians to care for them, as compared to those living in cities.⁽⁴⁵⁾ According to the chart book, rural USA residents often have some unhealthy behaviors; often, they smoke more, exercise less, have less nutritional diets, and are more likely to be obese than urban residents.⁽⁴⁶⁾

In the same context, other studies reported that rural residents, due to occupational exposure, such as toxic substances largely used in agriculture, have a greater risk of several types of cancers,⁽⁴⁷⁾ respiratory diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and musculoskeletal pain.⁽⁴⁸⁾ Other studies also reported that rural residents have a higher risk of neurologic diseases such as Parkinson's disease, or cognitive decline and dementia.⁽⁴⁹⁾ On the other hand, a few studies suggested that the rural population suffered less from health problems like cardiovascular diseases^(47,50) and may have, as

compared to their urban peers, a healthier lifestyle, such as a lower tobacco consumption,^(51,52) greater physical activity due to the pursuance of agricultural activities, gardening, walking, fishing, hunting⁽⁵³⁾, and specific dietary habits that may be rich in fruits and vegetables,⁽⁴⁹⁾ but the scarce literature addressing this specific population shows inconsistent results.

Differences in frailty between rural and urban older people have been demonstrated in developed countries. One study in a rural area in the Andes Mountains of Colombia, involving 1878 participants aged 60 years and over, elder shown to be frail, frailty appeared to be strongly associated with comorbidities.⁽⁵⁴⁾ Song et al., in a Canadian study, reported that there was a difference in deficit accumulation between rural and urban areas, but this difference decreased with increased age.⁽⁵⁵⁾ In a large longitudinal study concerning Frailty and survival of older Chinese adults in urban and rural areas, urban dwellers showed a better survival rate than their counterparts in the rural areas.⁽⁵⁶⁾

In Lebanon, with the lack of literature concerning the health status in rural areas, where most of the inhabitants are located there is an absence of policies and pension system,⁽⁵⁷⁾ with high cost of health insurances as well as health disparities, and where a significant percentage of Lebanese households living in poverty or below the poverty line (between 52.5 percent to 19 percent pursuant to their place of residence).⁽⁵⁸⁾ These facts point to the need for more investigation. Studies of health conditions of these rural populations are deemed urgent and critical.

The impaired health status of older people contributes to an increase in vulnerability, especially that the percent of people classified with a high percentage of illiteracy, there is a direct correlation between poverty and literacy.⁽⁵⁹⁾

Unfortunately, little is known about the health status, characteristics and needs of older people in rural Lebanon. Most of the published studies involved older adults in nursing homes^(60,61) not in primary care, for which consultation times and multidisciplinary resources were limited.

The recurring challenges in geriatrics today for all countries are identifying those elderly persons who are in need of geriatric interventions, medical care and support. In order to adapt their health care systems to meet the challenges associated with population aging, most of the developed and developing countries are showing an increased interest in addressing frailty. Frailty screening in the context of the primary and healthcare community is fundamental, in order to ensure the dignity and quality of life of older persons.^(28,30)

1.5 Research Questions

1. What is the prevalence of frailty in rural Lebanon?
2. Are the prevalence rates comparable to those of other developing countries in the region?
3. Are Lebanese citizens residing in rural areas exposed to similar risk factors, as experienced in other countries?

1.6 Objectives

This study is aimed at:

1. Identifying the prevalence of frailty (full syndrome and pre-frail stage) among older people residing in rural areas of Lebanon.
2. Determining risk factors for the development of frailty among rural Lebanese residents.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 History of Frailty

From 1986, the term "frailty" started to appear with increasing frequency in the gerontological literature, but there appears to be no consensus as to what the term actually means.

Historically, the term frailty was fluctuating between a narrow definition and a broad one. While Stamford used the term synonymously with institutionalization,⁽⁶²⁾ frailty was defined, in 1978, in terms of a broad age range when the Federal Council on the Aging (FCA), USA, considered that it is an accompaniment of increasing age. Frailty meant reduction of physical and emotional capacities and loss of - a social - support system to the extent that the elderly individual becomes unable to maintain household or social contacts – without continuing assistance from others.⁽⁶³⁾

In 1988, Woodhouse and associates⁽⁶⁴⁾ defined frail elderly people as those aged 65 years and over who depended on others for the activities of daily living and were often under institutional care. Gillick⁽⁶⁵⁾ (1989), defined frail elderly people as "old debilitated individuals who cannot survive without substantial help from others," emphasizing the social consequences of frailty. Others focused on frailty as measured by disability, particularly difficulties in performing activities of daily living.⁽³⁾

Both the broad and narrow definitions of frailty present problems with conceptual clarity and focus. If older persons are characterized as frail, it would be better to simply talk about problems associated with aging. In parallel, using the term for a particular outcome is more precise and hence more useful in problem description when frailty is narrowly associated with one outcome, such as institutionalization or disability. Ultimately, frailty is not "all-or-nothing." Equating frailty with aging, disability and vulnerability seems to be confounding.

Rockwood et al (1994)⁽⁶⁷⁾ seemed to have captured the essence of frailty when his team added the important controlling principle of a precarious, easily perturbed balance between the assets maintaining health and the deficits threatening it. The perturbation of balance causes the patient to go into hospital or other institution for care.

Furthermore, Campbell⁽⁶⁸⁾ defined frailty in more complex terms, as a condition or syndrome that results from a multisystem reduction in reserve capacity, to the extent that a number of physiological systems are close to, or pass, the threshold of symptomatic clinical failure. Frailty can be diagnosed clinically by measuring four key capacities required for successful interaction with the environment: musculoskeletal function, aerobic capacity, cognitive and integrative neurological function and nutritional state.

An operational definition of frailty based on a Cardiovascular Health Study (CHS) was presented by Fried and colleagues (2001)⁽²⁷⁾, in which they conceptualized frailty as a syndrome of decreased resiliency and reserves, whereby a mutually exacerbating cycle of declines across multiple systems results in a negative energy balance, sarcopenia, and diminished strength and tolerance for exertion. Accordingly, the syndrome proposes that persons exhibit exhaustion, weight loss, weak grip strength, slow walking speed, and low energy expenditure as frailty-identifying characteristics.

Alternatively, Mitnitski et al., using data from a cross-sectional Study of Health and Aging conducted in Canada, operationalized frailty as a risk index by counting the number of deficits accumulated over time (termed "frailty index (FI)"), including disability, diseases, physical and cognitive impairments, psychosocial risk factors, and geriatric syndromes.⁽⁶⁹⁾

While Rockwood et al. suggest, as opposed to Fried's frailty Phenotype, that the FI is a more sensitive predictor of adverse health outcomes.⁽⁷⁰⁾ Xue, in his manuscript, focused on Fried's Phenotype. This 5-component phenotype method seems to be more appealing for use in a clinical setting than the FI that typically contains 30 - 70 items.⁽⁷¹⁾

In 2012, the Conference on Frailty and Sarcopenia convened in Orlando, Florida, USA, and based on the International Association of Gerontology and Geriatrics and World Health Organization White Paper, recognized that: physical frailty is an important medical syndrome, which simple screening tests are available for screening in order to identify persons with physical frailty or at risk of frailty. The physical frailty is a manageable condition for which all persons older than 70 years should be screened.

2.2 Frailty Differs from Aging

Aging can be defined as the decline and deterioration of functional properties at the cellular, tissue and organ level. This decrease of functional properties yields a loss of performance and homeostasis, decreased adaptability to internal and external stress, which may yield an increased vulnerability to morbidity and mortality.^(72, 73)

As people age, they accumulate impairments in multiple physiological systems and become increasingly vulnerable to adverse outcomes. This process of vulnerability and decline is inextricably linked to the aging process.^(29,31)

Nevertheless, the conceptualization of frailty may help in understanding the heterogeneity of functional decline observed with chronological aging.⁽⁷⁴⁾ With aging, some people appear to be frail at age 70 years, whereas others only reach this state in their 90s.

Some studies have reported that individual mortality risk, which can be seen as the ultimate outcome of age and frailty, can be better predicted by frailty than by chronological age.⁽⁷⁵⁾

Frailty is considered as a better predictor of autonomy, institutionalization, and mortality. Studies have shown that some degree of functional loss is inevitable with old age, with the risk of adverse outcomes being established by age 70.⁽⁷⁶⁾

In contrast, other studies suggest that some or all of the manifestations of frailty are caused by an underlying process, separate from aging, but is most likely to develop and progress with aging.⁽⁷⁷⁾

2.3 Frailty Differs from Disability

Both disability and frailty are rather prevalent in older populations, and have common characteristics of multi-factorial nature, and share some risk factors and pathophysiological mechanisms.⁽⁷⁸⁾

As the population ages, disability, defined as a social phenomenon, is becoming an increasingly important medical concept as regards public health consequences such as adverse health outcomes and increasing costs, as well as an impaired quality of life of the older population.⁽⁷⁹⁾

Vitality and health statistics, based on data from the National Health Interview Survey in 1994, have reported that 20%–30% of community-dwelling adults aged older than 70 years are disabled in mobility, IADLs (tasks essential to independent household management, such as meal preparation, shopping, and managing money) and/or ADLs (basic self-care tasks, such as bathing, dressing, and eating); the frequency of disability rises steadily with age among those aged 65 years and older.^(80,81)

Ferrucci et al. described the progressive versus catastrophic disability in a longitudinal view of the disablement process, and indicated that about half of the disability cases develop slowly, usually in

association with chronic disease, co-morbidities, and frailty; in the other half of the cases, the disablement process is abrupt.⁽⁸²⁾

In clinical practice, disabled elderly people are often described interchangeably as dependent, with multiple chronic conditions, co-morbid, or frail. All these terms are describing the most physically vulnerable of the elderly population in need of enhanced care.

In order to find a clinical consensus, a survey was conducted among 62 geriatricians by Fried et al.⁽³¹⁾, which asked about terms of frailty and disability. Ninety-eight (98) percent of the respondents felt that frailty and disability are 'not the same'. However, the causal relationships were not as clear: disability was understood by responding geriatricians to be the cause of frailty (88%), as well as its consequence (90%). This clinical inconsistency reflects frequent overlapping of co-morbidity, disability and frailty, which was also confirmed by the results of the Cardiovascular Health Study⁽²⁷⁾ noted earlier.

These three conditions (co-morbidity, disability and frailty) seem to be interrelated, in that frailty could contribute to the progression of chronic diseases; frailty and co-morbidity could predict subsequent disability; disability may lead to frailty and worsen co-morbidity.

Research has shown that the terms co-morbidity, disability and frailty are commonly used interchangeably to identify vulnerable older people. A consensus that these are distinct clinical entities causally related with different prognosis and health care implications was argued by Fried et al.⁽³¹⁾

2.4 Frailty Differs from Co-morbidity

Compared with disability and frailty, co-morbidity should be the most straightforward concept to define medically.

In general, the term co-morbidity has three meanings:

1. Two or more medical conditions exist simultaneously regardless of their casual relationship;
2. Two or more medical conditions exist simultaneously and interdependently of each other, which means that one medical condition causes, is caused by, or is otherwise related to another condition in the same individual;
3. Two or more medical conditions exist simultaneously but independently of each other. In this sense, the concept of co-morbidity could be viewed as the more traditional medical definition of disease and as an interface between the geriatric paradigms of health.⁽³¹⁾

With aging, the presence of co-morbidity increases markedly, in large part because the frequency of individual chronic conditions rises with age. For example, after age 65, 13.4% of community-dwelling persons in Lebanon report arthritis, 36.7% hypertension, 23.1% heart disease, 21.5% diabetes, 9.7% chronic backache, and 6% a history of stroke. As a result of these diseased subpopulations within the general population in Lebanon, 77.1% older than 65 years reports at least one disease.⁽¹⁰⁾ Co-morbidity is associated with higher health care utilization and expenditures,⁽³¹⁾ and also heightens the risk of disability and mortality.⁽⁸³⁾

Fried et al. indicated that co-morbidity could be defined as the aggregation of clinically manifest diseases present in an individual, and frailty as the aggregate of subclinical losses of reserve across multiple physiologic systems. Without dismissing that co-morbidity^(84,83) and frailty⁽²⁷⁾ are independent risk factors for disability.

In the same context, in a cross-sectional study among 740 community-dwelling elderly people from the Montreal Unmet Needs Study (MUNS), Wong et al.⁽⁸⁵⁾ reported that 7.4% were classified as frail and

that frailty was associated with age, gender, income, education, number of chronic diseases, decreased ADL disability, and IADL disability. Among those classified as frail, 29.1% had disabilities in ADLs, 92.7% in IADLs and 81.8% had co-morbidity. Researchers noted that these findings support previous studies, and provide further evidence that although frailty seems to be a distinct geriatric concept, it also overlaps with other concepts.

2.5 Pathophysiology of Frailty

Whereas several research papers had reported that genetics, disease, injuries, lifestyle and aging may be considered as causative elements of frailty,^(27,86,87) other research had yielded that there were no specific causes for frailty.⁽⁸⁸⁾

In fact, some researchers consider frailty as a disorder of multiple inter-related physiological systems. When with aging there is a gradual decline in physiological reserve to compensate a disability, in frailty, this decline is accelerated. Compensatory mechanisms start failing, with high risk of homeostasis disruption and consequent negative health outcomes.⁽⁸⁹⁾

Clegg et al.⁽²⁸⁾, in a paper published in *The Lancet*, reported that the running of the complex mechanisms of aging should be considered when addressing the pathophysiology of frailty. Aging mechanisms promote cumulative decline in multiple physiological systems, subsequent erosion of homeostatic reserves, and vulnerability to disproportionate changes in health status following relatively minor stressor events. These complex aging mechanisms are influenced by underlying genetic and environmental factors, in combination with epigenetic mechanisms that regulate the differential expression of genes in cells and may be especially important in aging.

While Fried et al. proposed an operational definition by which individuals are considered to be frail, there is also evidence that frailty may result from pathologic processes that act independently from the effects of diseases present in the elderly. Many reports indicate that frailty is associated with elevated circulating levels of markers of inflammation (C-reactive protein) and coagulation (fibrinogen and factor VIII)⁽⁹⁰⁾, tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF α), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and fibrinogen⁽⁹¹⁾. These markers were linked to frailty even in the absence of two of the most prevalent co-morbid conditions in older persons, cardiovascular disease and diabetes⁽⁹⁰⁾. Such studies found associations between elevations in inflammatory markers and low muscle strength, exhaustion, slow walking speed, and low physical activity, confirming the suggestion of Szanton, Allen, Seplaki, Bandeen-Roche, and Fried in 2009⁽⁹²⁾ concerning the AL index (Allostatic Load). All major regulatory systems, such as biomarkers of cardiovascular, metabolic, endocrine, and inflammatory markers, represented in the AL index are linked to individual indicators of frailty.

Thus, frailty is independently associated with an absolute number of impaired physiological systems; as more systems show abnormal function, frailty increases, and a dysregulation in a complex network of interaction occurs between its biological elements.

Zaslavsky et al.⁽⁸⁸⁾ suggested that the pathophysiological mechanisms of frailty run throughout three levels: Level I – Cellular Changes, Level II – System Dysregulation, and Level III – System Impairment.

2.5.1 Level I - Cellular Changes

At the cellular level, while cumulative oxidative damage had been considered by researchers as one of the plausible causal pathways leading to frailty,⁽⁹⁰⁾ some studies reported that the loss of telomeres, with resultant alterations in cell division and protein production, had been strongly associated with physiological decline in older adults.⁽⁹³⁾ Multiple studies supported such a hypothesis, concerning the

impact of cellular changes on frailty, although others declined it. Therefore, additional research is needed to further explore the molecular foundations of frailty.⁽⁸⁸⁾

2.5.2 Level II - System Dysregulation

A number of studies have helped to establish inflammation, hormonal dysregulation, activation of blood clotting pathways, and metabolic abnormalities as important correlates of frailty.^(94,95)

Taking into consideration the inflammatory process, the aging immune system is characterized by a decline in stem cells, alterations in T-lymphocyte production, blunting of the B-cell led antibody response, and reduced phagocytic activity of neutrophils, macrophages and natural killer cells. This senescent immune system may function adequately in the quiescent state, but fail to respond appropriately to the stress of acute inflammation.⁽²⁸⁾ Evidence, reported by different studies, suggests that inflammatory pathway alterations play a crucial pathophysiological role in the development of frailty and chronic disease. Cross-sectional data from the CHS cohort revealed that frail versus non-frail participants had significantly increased levels of CRP.⁽⁹⁵⁾ Other longitudinal analyses assessing the risk of frailty after 5 and 9 years of follow-up yielded similar results, demonstrating that CRP levels at the baseline were significantly associated with incident frailty.⁽⁸⁸⁾

As well as the endocrine system, it is reported that alterations in anabolic hormones are closely linked to a state of multisystem senescence, and are theorized to contribute to aging and frailty. A study conducted by Capolla et al.⁽⁹⁶⁾ suggested that these effects are mediated through musculoskeletal impairment; however, further confirmatory research is needed. As regards the hematocoagulatory status, research reveals that activation of coagulation and fibrinolytic systems play a role in the pathophysiology of frailty in older people, which may have a significant role in preventing or at least slowing the downward cascade toward frailty.⁽⁸⁸⁾

In summary, it has become apparent that inflammatory, endocrine, coagulation, and metabolic pathways are increasingly disrupted with advanced age and, to a greater extent, in those who meet the criteria for frailty. The coexistence of these unbalanced factors suggests their synergistic role in pathophysiological mechanisms leading to frailty.⁽⁸⁸⁾

2.5.3 Level III - System Impairment

The consideration of multisystem impairment in frailty is consistent with the wide range of studies on different factors associated with its development.

Musculoskeletal impairment is defined as the loss of muscle mass, strength and power classically seen in frailty that is closely associated with the development of sarcopenia, which leads to mobility loss and a decrease in gait speed.⁽⁹⁷⁾

Neurocognitive impairment has been reported to be strongly associated with a functional decline. Likewise, sensory impairment, psychological factors, mood disturbance (such as depression) that lead to a high rate of disability, hospitalization and mortality, have been suggested as indicators of frailty^(88,98).

2.6 Frailty as Predictor of Adverse Health Outcome

Most practitioners of medicine have been trained to focus on specific medical diseases when approaching a patient. Frailty does not fit neatly into that practice pattern, because it is almost never the basis for a ‘‘chief complaint’’, and its presence is often subtle or asymptomatic.⁽⁹⁹⁾ Elderly patients with declining health pose significant challenges for attending physicians; often the cause or causes of the deterioration in health are not identifiable nor reversible.

The term frailty has been used to characterize the weakest and most vulnerable subset of older adults.⁽⁹⁰⁾ Recent research efforts have helped to better define clinical and physiological characteristics of frailty and to highlight the vulnerability of frail, older adults to poor health outcomes. Studies also sought to ascertain whether identification of frailty stages can predict any adverse outcome.

Despite a lack of consensus on definition or measurement, frailty indicators predict adverse outcomes in older people. Coelho et al.⁽²⁴⁾, in a study conducted among 252 community-dwelling elderly individuals in three northern Portuguese cities, reported that the physical components of frailty seem to have a greater importance for the prediction of adverse health outcomes.

As reported in the literature, the impact of concurrent frailty and CHF is evident, given that the prevalence of CHF increases six- to seven-fold with increasing frailty severity.^(100,101) Since frailty is likely to be multidimensional, studies conducted in urban and rural areas in China, Mexico and Peru, and urban areas in Cuba, Dominican Republic, Venezuela and India have shown that frailty is an indicator that identifies older people at risk of dependence, morbidity and mortality.⁽¹⁰²⁾

A study conducted by Khandelwal et al.⁽¹⁰³⁾ showed that frailty also has an impact on hospitalized persons, concluding that almost a third of hospitalized older patients are frail, and have anemia, higher frequency of CHF, cognitive impairment, require longer hospital stay, and have a higher mortality rate. A similar prospective cohort study⁽¹⁰⁴⁾ conducted in hospital settings among 220 acute in-patients with arterial fibrillation, showed that compared to non-frail patients, frail ones were significantly more likely to experience embolic stroke, had a small non-significant increase in risk of major hemorrhage and had a higher risk of mortality.

While the predictions of adverse health outcome remain challengeable, studies use different approaches to determine frailty tools and to demonstrate the use of frailty identification to predict diseases and pathologies.

2.7 Tools for Predicting Frailty, and Their Validities

Numerous frailty definitions and assessment tools have been developed in clinical practice and research, and this has been the focus of many reviews and comparative studies.^(37,70) In particular, the Frailty Phenotype of Fried et al.^(27,70) has achieved international reputation. The method has been extensively validated in research literature.^(92,105)

As noted earlier, the main advantage of Fried's method is that it requires the measurement of only five variables, namely weight loss, exhaustion, grip strength, walking speed and physical activity.⁽²⁷⁾

In Fried's definition, frailty is defined in terms of three categories, each of which is defined by the sum of the number of individual criteria present (0: non-frail, 1 or 2: pre-frail, and 3, 4 or 5: frail), as will be explained extensively in the section on Methodology. In fact, Fried's criteria are considered as the golden standard. Several studies employed it as a referral scale to measuring the validity of all other scales concerning the screening of frailty, although many researchers had developed other tools to predict frailty, such as Frailty Index, Share Scale, Frail Scale, Groningen Frailty Index, and SOF Index, as alluded to in the following:

2.7.1 The Frailty Index

Frailty Index (FI)⁽¹⁰⁶⁾ is also a multidimensional screening instrument, which was developed around the same time as the Frailty Phenotype. The FI is measured by comparing the ratio of health deficits present within an individual to possible health deficits, using a pre-specified list of health conditions. The FI allows the inclusion of any health deficit, provided that a minimum of 30 deficits in total are included and that each deficit is associated with adverse health outcomes.

While it was argued that, compared to Fried's Frailty Phenotype, the FI is a more sensitive predictor of adverse health outcomes, due to its finer graded risk scale, and its robustness in clinical inferences with regard to the number and actual composition of the items in the FI ⁽⁷⁰⁾, the 5-component Phenotype method is more appealing for use in a clinical setting than the FI that typically contains 30-70 items.⁽⁷¹⁾

2.7.2 The SHARE Scale

Santos-Eggimann et al. employed an approach to Fried's method in the first wave of the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), in order to establish the prevalence of frailty in middle-aged and older community-dwelling Europeans in ten different countries.⁽³³⁾

Like Fried's Phenotype, SHARE embraced the following five criteria but with some modifications:

1. **Exhaustion** was identified as a positive response to the question "In the last month, have you had too little energy to do things you wanted to do? (Yes/No)."
2. **The Shrinking** criterion was fulfilled by reporting a "diminution in the desire for food" in response to the question "What has your appetite been like?" or, in the case of a non-codable response to this question, by responding "less" to the following question: "Have you been eating more or less than usual?"
3. **Weakness** was derived from the highest of four consecutive dynamometer measurements of handgrip strength (two for each hand), applying gender and body mass index cutoffs set by Fried and associates.
4. **Slowness** was defined using mobility questions: "Because of a health problem, do you have difficulty [expected to last more than 3 months] walking 100 m?" or "... climbing one flight of stairs without resting?"
5. **The low activity** criterion was fulfilled when participants responded "one to three times a month" or "hardly ever or never" to the question "How often do you engage in activities that require a low or moderate level of energy, such as gardening, cleaning the car, or going for a walk?"

Similar to Fried's Phenotype method, one point was allocated for each fulfilled criterion: individuals with zero points were classified as non-frail, those with one or two points as pre-frail, and those with three to five points as frail.

Another study applying the SHARE instrument was conducted by Romero-Ortuno et al.⁽³⁹⁾ in the same 10 European countries, in order to validate it. Results showed that the SHARE Frailty Instrument demonstrated sufficient constructive and predictive validity of frailty in primary care.

2.7.3 The FRAIL Scale

The FRAIL scale includes 5 components: Fatigue, Resistance, Ambulation, Illness, and Loss of weight.⁽¹⁰⁷⁾ Frail Scale scores range from 0–5, with 1 point for each component; like Fried's Phenotype, where frail individuals had a score of (3-5), pre-frail ones a score of (1–2), and robust ones a score of (zero).

In this study, fatigue was measured by asking respondents how many times during the past 4 weeks they felt tired; the responses of "all of the time" or "most of the time" scoring 1 point. Resistance was assessed by asking participants if they had any difficulty walking up to 10 steps alone without resting and without aid, with "yes" responses scoring 1 point. Ambulation was assessed by asking if they had any difficulty walking several hundreds of yards alone and without aids, with "yes" responses scoring 1

point. Illness was scored as 1 point for respondents who reported 5 or more illnesses from a total of 11 illnesses. Loss of weight was scored as 1 point for respondents with a weight decline of 5% or more within the past 12 months based on self-report.

2.7.4 The Groningen Frailty Index

The Groningen Frail Index (GFI) is a 15-item instrument to determine the level of frailty, which is available in both a professional and a self-report version. It measures the loss of functions and resources in 4 domains: physical (mobility functions, multiple health problems, physical fatigue, vision, and hearing), cognitive (cognitive dysfunction), social (emotional isolation), and psychological (depressed mood and feelings of anxiety).

A cross-sectional study was conducted among 359 elderly persons residing in the northern provinces of The Netherlands, in order to identify the validity of the Groningen Frailty Index (GFI). Researchers reported that, as compared to non-frail participants, frail older persons had higher levels of case complexity, disability, and a lower quality of life and life satisfaction. In this study, the feasibility, reliability, and validity of the self-assessment version of the GFI in home-dwelling and institutionalized elderly people were confirmed.⁽¹⁰⁸⁾

2.7.5 The SOF index

The SOF index^(109,110) identified frailty as the presence of 2 or more of the following 3 components during the second examination:

1. Weight loss (irrespective of intention to lose weight) of 5% or more between the baseline and the second examination (mean number of years between examinations 3.4 (\pm 0.5));
2. Inability to rise from a chair five times without using one's arms; and
3. Poor energy when answering "no" to the question "Do you feel full of energy?", as based on the Geriatric Depression Scale.

Alternatively, Kiely et al.⁽¹¹²⁾, in a prospective observational study that was conducted within the framework of MOBILIZE Boston among 765 community-dwelling participants, reported that both the SOF and CHS frailty measurement instruments were similar in their ability to predict key geriatric outcomes, such as recurrent overnight hospitalization, emergency room visits, and disability, as well as chronic medical conditions, physical function, cognitive disability, and depression. Noteworthy is that both the SOF and CHS indexes provide good measures of frailty; however, the simpler SOF index may prove easier and more practical in a clinical setting.

2.8 Interventions to Prevent Frailty

Little is known about the natural course of frailty. Many studies are performed to determine the transition rates between states of frailty and to evaluate the effect of the preceding state of frailty on subsequent frailty transitions.

Also, little is known about the likelihood of transitions between different states of frailty (robust, pre-frail, frail). In the Cardiovascular Health Study (CHS), the 4-year incidence of frailty was 7.2% among participants who were initially non-frail.⁽²⁷⁾

A prospective cohort study, which was conducted using Fried Phenotype, yielded that frailty among older persons is a dynamic process, characterized by frequent transitions between states of frailty over time. Transitions to states of greater frailty were more common than transitions to states of lesser frailty, and the probability of transitioning from being frail to non-frail was very low, even over an

extended period of time. Importantly, the likelihood of transitioning between states of frailty was highly dependent on one's preceding state of frailty.⁽⁴¹⁾

The transition from the pre-frail state (latent phase) to the frail state (clinically apparent) is generally marked or provoked by a trigger event, such as an injury, an acute disease and/or psychological stress.⁽¹¹²⁾

As frailty is a progressive condition that begins with a preclinical stage, there are opportunities for early detection and prevention.⁽³¹⁾ Since the preclinical stage of the frailty process is latent and clinically silent and not apparently linked with any disease condition, it remains difficult to detect. On the other hand, the clinical frailty stage could be detected by a suitable assessment tool.⁽¹¹²⁾

The prevention of frailty is the ultimate aim. It is possible to differentiate frailty, which seems to be reversible, from aging, which is not reversible. Interventions have been made in older people that target correlations or specific components of frailty. Lebel et al.⁽¹¹³⁾ proposed an approach to combat frailty in six different modes:

1. Adequate diet with sufficient protein, vitamin and mineral intake.
2. Regular physical exercise, practiced alone or in groups, such as stretching, walking, dancing, dynamic balance exercise and lifting weights.
3. Regular monitoring of individual basic abilities, such as walking, balance, and cognition.
4. Prevention of infections by the flu, pneumococcal and herpes zoster vaccines.
5. Anticipation of stressful events such as elective surgery
6. Rapid reconditioning after stressful events via re-nutrition and individually tailored physiotherapy.

Lang et al.⁽¹¹²⁾ reported that frailty can be differentiated from aging, but unlike aging, it can be prevented and possibly reversed. In fact, in an observational cross-sectional study performed in Spain among 324 community-dwelling people aged 75 years and older, the authors suggested that low physical activity is also related to frailty and predisposes to positive energy balance and obesity. Moreover, they recommended that health professionals must encourage older people to exercise regularly and maintain good dietary habits, including both good calories and protein intake, and good micronutrient intake of fruits and vegetables.

Another review was conducted to address the role of physical activity with a focus on providing evidence for the benefits of both physical activity and exercise on preventing frailty. This review suggested that many results suggest that moderate physical activity carried out as part of everyday activities can be of substantial benefit even to frail and older persons. Vigorous exercises are not always required, while regular leisure activities – such as walking, gardening, or housekeeping – seem to be enough to reach considerable benefits.⁽¹¹⁴⁾

In the same context, six systematic reviews were published specifically on the benefits of exercise in frail older adults. In some cases, clinical trials did not show any convincing evidence of effectiveness, while in others the main conclusion was that exercise can improve partial aspects of functional outcomes in frail persons, such as: sit-to-stand performance, balance, agility, and ambulation. The lack of consistency among the studies is due to the differences in the definition of frailty, training protocols, and characteristics of the inactive groups. Thus, a definite conclusion has not yet been reached.⁽¹¹⁵⁾

Further, many studies were conducted to define the relationship between frailty and nutrition. In a review⁽¹¹⁶⁾ of 24 studies into clinical interventions, which evaluated the effectiveness of nutrition interventions on frailty indicators, the results revealed that modification of nutrition quality, either by giving supplements or by improving diet intake, could improve strength, walking speed, and nutritional

status in the majority of frail or pre-frail older adults. However, there was limited evidence on the effectiveness of intervention on inflammatory status and other biomarkers related to frailty due to limited number of studies targeting frailty biomarkers as a major outcome.

Puts et al.⁽¹¹⁷⁾ reported that the best interventions to prevent or reduce the level of frailty, maintain functional status and quality of life, reduce healthcare costs, and enable older people to continue living at home, are currently unknown.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design

A cross-sectional study was conducted among 340 community-dwelling older people aged 65 years and over in a rural area in Lebanon, in the Shouf district; it was carried out between June and September 2016. Participants were recruited randomly following informed signed consent; signed by each individual. Persons who reported dementia or who lacked capacity for consent were recruited on the basis of a relative's signed agreement. The information sheet and the consent form were being read to illiterate persons when they were invited to express their approval verbally, which was witnessed. Questions had been simplified in different manners and were repeated many times with good spelling for patients with self-reported dementia and suffering from a hearing impairment.

Noteworthy is that the participation rate was 88.33%, and the study received an approval from the ethics committee of the Institutional Review Board at Ain Wazein Medical Village, Lebanon, on May 13, 2016.

3.2 Sample Size Calculation

Several studies that focus on frailty estimate its prevalence to vary between 4% and 59.1%.⁽³²⁾ The estimated prevalence of frailty in Lebanon in 2013 was estimated to be 36.4%⁽¹¹⁸⁾, which was used to calculate the sample size using the equation: $n = (z^2 \times p(1 - p))/e^2$ with a confidence level of 95%, and a $\pm 5\%$ accuracy.

The population in the Shouf district at the time of the study was estimated to be 166,140 inhabitants.⁽¹¹⁹⁾ Of the total population, 8% (13,329 persons) were reported to be elderly people⁽¹²⁰⁾, i.e. the target population of the study.

The required sample size was calculated to be 340. Estimating that around 10-20% of the elderly people would not agree to participate, a total of 385 elders were recruited to participate, 45 of whom did not agree; this led to the required minimum sample size of 340.

3.3 Research Process

Generating a sampling frame and selecting participants are two of the most important steps in the survey research process. However, establishing the sampling frame, which entails identifying all cases that should have an equal probability of selection, is not always possible or practical in social science surveys.⁽¹²¹⁾ This is the case even in countries that have a tradition of collecting census data or large-scale survey studies.

In Lebanon, social scientists who wish to employ probability sampling in research face a number of challenges.⁽³⁾ First and foremost, census data in Lebanon has not been collected accurately. As such, accurate information on the population statistics and other socio-demographic characteristics of the Lebanese population is lacking.

As far as this is concerned, and in order to select the number of subjects to be interviewed in each village, the population from 75 Municipalities was estimated, following phone calls to the head of each municipality, based on the list of eligible voters.

The sample size to be recruited from each village was calculated based on the estimated number of elderly persons in each municipality, in order to have a proportionate sample based on the number of inhabitants per village.

3.4 Questionnaire

This study was based on a comprehensive multi-component questionnaire. The questionnaire was translated back and forth from English to Arabic by two persons fluent in both languages.

A pilot trial was performed on 10 individuals prior to data collection, in order to pretest the feasibility of the questionnaire. Based to these results, a few minor changes were made. Individuals were interviewed and selected randomly from each village. Participants who met the age criteria (65 or over), and who lived in their own home were considered to be included in the study. Participants remained anonymous and individual results were kept confidential. The interview duration of 30–40 minutes was considered acceptable. If the participant was unable to answer the entire research questionnaire, help from family members was sought. There was no response from 35 visited houses, and in 14 visited houses, all household members were aged below 65 (n=14).

3.4.1 Socio-Demographic Factors

The demographic characteristics used in this study include: age, gender, marital status and number of living children. The level of education was categorized as either illiterate, 8 years or less of education (Primary School), 8-12 years of education (Middle School), 12-15 years of education (High School), or University and advanced education.⁽¹²²⁾ Information about social status was assessed by a question about living alone, or the number of adults dwelling in the same house. Regarding main occupation, individuals were questioned if they are still working and about the longest occupation held, the responses to which were categorized into: without work (including household), agriculture sector, military sector, employee or manager, self-employed heavy activity, and self-employed light activity. The occupations were categorized according to their physical activity based on the Compendium of Physical Activity Tracking Guide 2000⁽¹²³⁾ and the Minnesota Leisure Time Activity Scale.⁽¹²⁴⁾

Financial status was assessed by three questions: firstly, whether there is a monthly income. If yes, then secondly the approximate height of the income, categorized as: less than 750,000 LL, 750,000-1,500,000 LL, and 1,500,000-3,000,000 LL or more. The third and final question focused on the level of dependency on family members as a money source, income from current work, stipend, one's own savings, total dependency on family members, or more than one source of income (partially dependent).

3.4.2 Geriatric Health Characteristics

Health related characteristics were assessed by the self-related health status questionnaire (SHR), based on a 5-item scale (excellent, very good, good, fair and poor). This measure has been shown to be a reliable indicator of health assessment in Arab countries⁽¹²⁵⁾, as well as in developed countries.⁽¹²⁶⁾

Co-morbidities were recorded by asking participants if they suffer from any chronic health conditions, such as cardiac disease, lung disease, thyroid disease, diabetes, cerebrovascular disease (CVA), dementia, Parkinson's disease, liver disease, kidney disease, osteoarthritis or any disc hernia, osteoporosis, or any other disease.

The number of medications currently consumed was estimated based on the number of medications taken on a regular basis as prescribed by a physician, “*or self prescribed*”; this information was checked by the interviewer, who also documented any steroids intake or that of any diet supplements. In addition, participants were questioned if they suffer from any vision or hearing impairment, any dental difficulty, any problem of chewing or swallowing food, any urinary or stool incontinence, or chronic diarrhea. They were also asked about the number of meals they take per day and if they had any falls in the last year, as well as any recent hospitalization and, if so, the length of stay in the hospital.

Furthermore, participants were questioned if they suffer from any chronic pain and, if so, they were asked to grade their pain on a Likert pain scale ranging from 0 to 10. Likewise, answers to questions about any diet consultations, about their primary referral physician, his specialty, the number of clinic visits during the last year, as well as any major barriers to clinic visits were reported.

Health life style was assessed by posing 3 questions. Firstly, participants were questioned if they do any physical exercise, alone or in groups in their villages. Secondly, if they are an ex or current smoker, and how many packets they smoke per day and, if they have quit smoking, how many years they had smoked. Thirdly, they were questioned about their alcohol drinking habits (never, occasionally, 2 to 3 times per week, more than 4 times per week, every day, more than 2 times per day).⁽¹²⁷⁾

3.4.3 Physical Functioning Assessment

Physical functioning was investigated through the Activities of Daily Living (ADL) Arabic version, which is an instrument that screens elderly respondents for their level of physical functioning and whether they are dependent or independent in their daily activities.

The ADL scale assesses overall physical functional activities such as bathing, dressing, going to the toilet, transferring (movement), continence, and feeding. For each component a score of 0, 0.5 or 1 is given according to the status of dependency: respectively, totally dependent, needs help with some issues, or self-reliant. The total ADL score, which is the sum of the aforementioned 6 activities, lies on an ordinal scale ascending from 0 to 6, where 6 entails complete independence and 0 complete dependence. The ADL scale Arabic version was validated by Nasser et Doumit in a sample of Lebanese elderly people living in nursing homes who did not have dementia.⁽¹²⁸⁾

The Lawton Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL) scale is an appropriate instrument to assess independent living skills. Participants were asked about eight activities: their ability to use the telephone, shopping, food preparation, housekeeping, laundry, mode of transportation, responsibility for own medication, ability to handle their finances. Persons were scored 0 to 1 point per activity, with summary scores ranging from 0 (low function, dependent) to 8 (high function, independent). The validation of this scale was developed by Lawton and Brody in 1969⁽¹²⁹⁾, and by Vittengel et al, for rural areas, in 2006.⁽¹³⁰⁾

3.4.4 Psychological and Cognitive Assessment

The 15-item mini GDS scale (Mini Geriatric Depression Scale) was used to detect depression disorders. It is a useful scale to detect depression among community-dwelling older people in primary care settings if the patients do not have dementia.⁽¹³¹⁾ The respondents have to answer 15 questions, using Yes/No answers, describing their feeling over the past week prior to the interview. A score of 0 to five is normal, a score greater than 5 suggests depression.

The cognitive status of the participants was assessed by the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE),⁽¹³²⁾ which is the most commonly used screening tool for cognitive impairment worldwide. It

is a 30-item scale that tests orientation, attention, immediate and short-term recall through verbal instructions. It is scored from 0 to 30. A score less than 24 indicates a mild cognitive impairment, and a score less than 17 a severe cognitive impairment. This scale, with a high sensitivity (82%) and specificity (80%).⁽¹³³⁾

3.4.5 Nutritional Assessment

The nutritional status of community-dwelling people was assessed using the Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA), which is the most validated screening tool for identifying nutritional status of elderly people, using a quick and easy format.⁽¹³⁴⁾

It consists of six questions as regards food intake, weight loss, mobility, psychological stress or acute disease, presence of dementia or depression, and body mass index (BMI). The presence of dementia or depression was assessed through MMSE and GDS results as described above. BMI is calculated from: weight (Kg)/(height (m))².

The nutritional status was regarded as normal if the MNA ranged between 12 and 14; as at risk of malnutrition when it ranged between 8 and 11; and as malnourished when it was below 7.

3.4.6 Frailty Assessment

Fried frailty criteria

Fried and colleagues developed five criteria (weight loss, exhaustion, low physical activity, slowness and weakness) to be used for identifying frail older people. A score of 0 or 1 should be given to each component of the frailty criteria according to their cut-off defined by Fried et al.⁽²⁷⁾ The sum of five criteria identifies the stage of frailty of each participant.

1. *Weight loss was assessed in two manners*

Weight loss was assessed using a two-step process: Firstly, by posing the question: “In the last year, have you lost more than 4.5 kg unintentionally? (i.e. not due to dieting or exercise)”; this criterion was met when the participant answered “yes”. Secondly, the weight of each participant was measured immediately during the interview using calibrated scales and asked to report their weight in the last year. Then, the K-weight was calculated as: (weight in previous year – current measured weight) / (weight in previous year). If $K \geq 0.05$ and the subject did not report that he/she was trying to lose weight, then the status frail as a result of weight loss was considered a “Yes”.

2. *Exhaustion (poor endurance and energy)*

When self-report indicated exhaustion, participants were required to answer the question “How often in the last week did you feel this way? by either a) I felt that everything I did was an effort; or (b) I could not get going”.⁽¹³⁵⁾

Subjects had to answer if they had this feeling for: less than one day, one or two days, three or four days, or most of the time on a weekly basis; and if subjects chose the answer three or more times a week, they were categorized as frail based on exhaustion criteria.

3. *Weakness*

Weakness was assessed by Hand Grip strength (kg) using a Dynamometer. Two consecutive measurements were taken from the hand most used. The average of 2-grip strengths was

adjusted for gender and body mass index (BMI); the cut-off was dependent on BMI. If the average was below the cut-off reported by Fried et al., the frailty criterion was met.

4. *Slowness*

Participants were asked to walk 6 meters, using a measuring stick consisting of a strip of wood with a straight edge, and the time interval in seconds was measured using a chronometer. This criterion was met when the time exceeded the cut-off reported by Fried et al., depending on gender and standing height.

5. *Physical activity*

Physical activity was assessed using the Minnesota Leisure-Time Physical Activity Questionnaire⁽¹²⁴⁾, which consists of a list of 63 sports, recreational, garden, and household activities. The participant was instructed to report whether or not they performed the activity in the last 12 months. The interviewer verified any “yes” responses and asked the participant “tell me in which months you performed them”, followed by “the average number of times per month” and “the average time spent on the activity each time you performed it”.

The 63 activities were divided into 8 categories: walking and miscellaneous, condition exercise, water activities, winter activities, sports, lawn and garden activities, home repair activities, fishing and hunting. The frequency of the activities was assessed month-by-month, as “average numbers of times per month”. Then, the Calories expended per week were calculated, stratified by gender to indicate if a participant was frail as a result of a physical activity or not. For Men: those with expended K-calories of physical activity per week < 383, and Women: those with K-calories per week < 270, were regarded as frail.⁽²⁷⁾ The stages of frailty were defined as follows: a score of 0 means that a person is robust (not frail). Persons with a score of 1 or 2 are at intermediate risk of adverse outcomes or are considered to be pre-frail. A score of 3–5 indicates that a person is frail.

3.5 Statistical Analysis

The aim of this study was to analyze the levels of functioning across various domains. The statistical package (SPSS) v16 was used for questionnaire data entry and statistical output. Descriptive statistics was carried out to describe the demographic and health characteristics, as well as the lifestyles. Outliers were determined and excluded from analysis, in order to provide a better picture of the study at hand.

Relationships between stages of frailty and a number of continuous variables were established, using Pearson correlation. Chi-square test was also used to study bivariate correlations between explanatory variables (socio-demographic indicators, physical, nutritional and mental health status,) and frailty stages. The relationships were also established separately for men and women, given that older women are more likely to be frail.

In order to reduce the number of misclassifications, only one missing value was allowed when a person had a valid Fried score of 0–2. If a person had a valid Fried score of 3 points or more, two missing values were allowed because, according to the Fried Phenotype method, this would not cause a misclassification.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Population (see Table 1)

The characteristics of the studied population are shown in Table 1. In total, 340 people (132 men (38.9%) and 208 women (61.1%)) aged between 65 and 97 years (76.2 ± 7.6 years) took part in the

study; the mean age for men was slightly higher than that for women. Of the sampled people, there were 36.8% persons aged between 75 and 84 years, and 17.9% older than 85 years. Most men (88.6%) were still married; 50% of women were widowers. About 19.1% of the elderly persons lived alone in their place of residence; it should be noted here that elderly women were three times more likely to live alone than men. Of the sampled population, 41.8% had a low level of education (under 8 years) and 39.1% were illiterate. With respect to profession, about 17% of the sampled population was self-employed, 14.7% were employees or managers, 49.7% did not work at all.

Of the sampled population, 12.6% (of whom 28% were male) were still working earning an income of 750,000 LL or less, 42.9% had a monthly income in the form of a stipend from the military or COOP, 51.4% had an income of between 750,000 and 1,500,000 LL.

It is noteworthy that 47.9% of the participants who did not benefit from any monthly income were totally dependent on their family members or relatives. The mean number of living children was 4.8, with a standard deviation of 2.2; the mean number of elderly persons who lived in the same household as their children was 1.8, with a standard deviation of 1. Some elderly persons were taken care of by housekeepers.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics by gender

VARIABLES	N/%	Total (N=340)	M (N=132)	F (N=208)	P
Age Mean (SD)		76.3(7.7)	77.9(7.8)	75.2(7.4)	<0.05
Age Class	N	340	132	208	
<i>Young Old</i>	%	45.3	36.4	51	<0.05
<i>Middle Old</i>	%	36.8	37.1	36.5	
<i>Old-Old</i>	%	17.9	26.5	12.5	
Marital Status	N	340	132	208	
<i>Single /divorced</i>	%	5.6	0.8	8.7	<0.05
<i>Married</i>	%	59.7	88.6	41.3	
<i>Widowed</i>	%	34.7	10.6	50	
Living Condition	N	340	132	208	
<i>Living Alone</i>	%	19.1	9.1	25.5	<0.05
<i>Living with others</i>	%	80.9	90.9	74.5	
No. of living children mean (SD)		4.8 (2.2)	4.8(2.0)	4.8(2.3)	
No. of adults in the same household mean		1.8 (1.0)	1.9(1.1)	1.7 (1.0)	
Level of Education	N	340	132	208	
<i>Illiterate</i>	%	39.1	31.1	44.2	<0.05
<i>8 years or less of Education (Primary</i>	%	41.8	46.2	38.9	
<i>8-12 years of education (Middle School)</i>	%	12.6	15.2	11.1	
<i>12-15 years of education (High School)</i>	%	5	6.1	4.3	
<i>University</i>	%	1.5	1.5	1.4	
Currently working	N	340	132	208	
<i>Yes</i>	%	12.6	28	2.9	<0.05
<i>No</i>	%	87.4	72	97.1	

Table 1 (cont.). Socio-demographic characteristics by gender

Old Occupation	N	340	132	208	
<i>Without Work (including Household)</i>	%	49.7	2.3	79.8	<0.05
<i>Agriculture</i>	%	8.8	18.9	2.4	
<i>Military</i>	%	9.4	24.2	0	
<i>Employee or Manager</i>	%	14.7	22	10.1	
<i>Self-employed Heavy Activity</i>	%	6.8	15.9	1	
<i>Self-employed Light Activity</i>	%	10.6	16.7	6.7	
Current Monthly Income	N	340	132	208	
<i>Yes</i>	%	42.9	56.8	34.1	<0.05
<i>no</i>	%	57.1	43.2	65.9	
Approximation Monthly Income	N	146	75	71	
<i><750,000</i>	%	40.4	40	40.8	0.82
<i>750,000-1,500,000</i>	%	51.4	53.3	79.3	
<i>1,500,000-3,000,000</i>	%	8.2	6.7	9.9	
Source of Income	N	340	132	208	
<i>Current work</i>	%	8.8	15.2	4.8	<0.05
<i>Stipend</i>	%	26.8	33.3	22.6	
<i>Using own saving</i>	%	11.8	15.2	9.6	
<i>More than one source (partially Dependent)</i>	%	4.7	3	5.8	
<i>Totally dependent on Family member</i>	%	47.9	33.3	57.2	

4.2 Results Regarding Health-Related Issues (see Tables 2, 3 and 4)

With respect to the self-rated health status scale, 50.6% of the studied persons perceived themselves to be in good health, 36.8% regarded their health as being poor, and about 12% considered themselves as being in very good or excellent health.

Chronic illness was reported by 84.7% of the sampled population, of whom 42.9% suffered from a cardiac disease, such as CHF, valvulopathies (diseases of the cardiac valves, coronary syndrome, 32.4% had diabetes, 26.8% suffered from joint and lumbosacral disease, including osteoarthritis, discal hernia, 22.6% reported a musculoskeletal disease like osteoporosis, 17.4% reported a lung disease, 12.6% a thyroid disease, 7.6% a CVA, and only 2.6% suffered from cancer.

As compared to men, elderly women suffered twice as much from joint disease and 7 times as much from musculoskeletal disease. In the same context, the proportion of women reporting pain was double that of men (55.3%), the same was true for severe pain (49.6%). There was a significant relationship between gender, chronic pain and pain severity ($p < 0.05$). The mean drug intake per day was 4.9 (SD 3.2); only 7.9% of the sample population took medication that contains steroids, and 13.8% took a diet supplement. Among both men and women, 77.6% reported a vision impairment and 59.1% reported a hearing impairment. Dental problems were reported by 64.1%, who complained about inappropriate dentures; chewing problems were reported by 25%, and 4.7% reported swallowing problems. Further, 38.2% of the sampled population suffered from urinary incontinence, and only 2.9% suffered from stool incontinence. While 45.3% of the population reported at least one fall during the last year, older

females (50%) seemed to have fallen more often than older men. There was a significant relationship between gender and falling ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2. Geriatric health assessment and co-morbidities by gender

VARIABLES	N/%	Total (N=340)	M (N=132)	F (N=208)	p
Current Health Status	N	340	132	208	
<i>Excellent</i>	%	3.2	5.3	1.9	<0.05
<i>Very Good</i>	%	9.4	16.7	4.8	
<i>Good</i>	%	50.6	54.5	48.1	
<i>Fair</i>	%	32.9	20.5	40.9	
<i>Poor</i>	%	3.8	3.0	4.3	
Chronic Disease	%	84.7	78.8	88.5	<0.05
<i>Cardiac Disease</i>	%	42.9	45.5	41.3	0.458
<i>Diabetes</i>	%	32.4	23.5	38.0	<0.05
<i>Joint and Lumbosacral Disease</i>	%	26.8	13.6	35.1	<0.05
<i>Musculoskeletal Disease</i>	%	22.6	4.5	34.1	<0.05
<i>Lung Disease</i>	%	17.4	15.2	18.8	0.394
<i>Thyroid Disease</i>	%	12.6	5.3	17.3	<0.05
<i>CVA</i>	%	7.6	13.6	3.8	<0.05
<i>Cancer</i>	%	2.6	1.5	3.4	0.302
<i>Parkinson Disease</i>	%	1.5	1.5	1.4	0.956
<i>Dementia</i>	%	1.5	2.3	1	0.330
<i>Kidney Disease</i>	%	4.1	3.8	4.3	0.808
<i>Liver Disease</i>	%	0.9	0.0	1.4	0.166
Poly-pharmacy mean (SD)		4.9 (3.2)	4.8 (3.1)	4.9 (3.2)	0.114
Diet supplement	%	13.8	12.1	14.9	0.470
Medication with Steroids	%	7.9	8.3	7.7	0.832
Vision impairment	%	77.6	73.5	80.3	0.144
Hearing impairment	%	59.1	68.2	53.4	<0.05
Chronic Pain	%	44.7	28	55.3	<0.05
Pain Scale mean (SD)		6.2 (1.7)	5.4 (1.9)	6.4 (1.6)	<0.05
Pain interpretation	N	152	37	115	
<i>Mild pain (1-3)</i>	%	3.9	13.5	0.9	<0.05
<i>Moderate pain (4-6)</i>	%	53.3	64.9	49.6	
<i>Severe pain (7-10)</i>	%	42.8	21.6	49.6	
Dental Problems	%	64.1	62.9	64.9	0.706
Chewing Problems	%	25	25.8	24.5	0.798
Swallowing Problems	%	4.7	11.4	11.1	0.930

Table 2 (cont.). Geriatric health assessment and co-morbidities by gender

Falls during the last year	%	45.3	37.9	50.0	<0.05
Urinary incontinence	%	38.2	40.9	36.5	0.420
Stool incontinence	%	2.9	3.8	2.4	0.464
Chronic diarrhea	%	4.7	3	5.8	0.246

Concerning follow up by health care providers, 57.1% reported that they always refer to the same physician. Regarding specialists, only 6.7% were regularly followed by a geriatrician regarding all health issues, 51.5% were followed by general practitioners, 23.2% by cardiologists, and 18.6% by other specialists. It is noteworthy that 3.8% of the people did not make regular visits to health care professionals.

Of the sample population, 22.9% had visited physicians more than 4 times per year. Furthermore, 75.2% of the sample population indicated that they did not make such regular visits, and about 16% regarded financial and transportation problems as their major barriers.

Table 3. Referring health care and hospitalization by gender

VARIABLES	N/%	Total- (N=340)	M (N=132)	F (N=208)	P
Dietary consultation	N	340	132	208	
<i>Yes</i>	%	10.3%	10.6%	10.1%	0.880
<i>No</i>	%	89.7%	89.4%	89.9%	
Visits to the Same Physician	N	340	132	208	
<i>No visits</i>	%	3.8	4.5	3.4	0.494
<i>Yes</i>	%	57.1	53	59.6	
<i>No</i>	%	39.1	42.4	37	
Specialty of referral physician	N	194	70	124	
<i>General Practitioner</i>	%	51.5	54.3	50	0.868
<i>Geriatrician</i>	%	6.7	5.7	7.3	
<i>Cardiologist</i>	%	23.2	24.3	22.6	
<i>Other</i>	%	18.6	15.7	20.1	
Number of visits to clinic in last year	N	340	132	208	
<i>Never</i>	%	30	43.2	21.6	<0.05
<i>1-3 visits</i>	%	47.1	40.9	51	
<i>4 and more visits</i>	%	22.9	15.9	27.4	
Major Barriers for visits	N	262	111	151	
<i>Financial issue</i>	%	10.6	7.2	13.2	0.306
<i>Transportation issue</i>	%	5.7	3.6	7.3	
<i>No need to visit a Doctor</i>	%	75.2	82	70.2	
<i>No requested appointment from physician</i>	%	2.3	2.7	2.1	
<i>More than 1 reason</i>	%	6.2	4.5	7.2	

Table 3 (cont.). Referring health care and hospitalization by gender

Number of hospitalizations mean (SD)	0.9 (1.4)	0.7 (1.3)	0.9 (1.5)	0.166
Length of stay in last year mean (SD)	2.2(3.6)	2.4 (4.5)	2.0 (2.9)	0.140

Concerning lifestyle and habits, 86.8% of the studied population did not perform any physical activity. About 10% of the people under study smoked, consuming one packet of cigarettes per day; 66.7% of the studied population quit smoking 10 years earlier.

Concerning alcohol consumption, 86.8% of the participants did not consume any alcohol at all; 12.1% did consume it occasionally.

Table 4. Lifestyle of the population by gender

VARIABLES	N/%	Total (N=340)	M(N=132)	F (N=208)	p
Number of meals per day (SD)		2.3 (0.6)	2.38 (0.6)	2.25 (0.6)	0.580
Physical Exercise	N	340	132	208	
<i>Yes</i>	%	13.2	15.2	12	0.408
<i>No</i>	%	86.8	84.8	88	
Smoke	N	340	132	208	
<i>Ex-smoker</i>	%	10.6	27.3	0	<0.05
<i>Current smoker</i>	%	10	15.2	6.7	
<i>Never smoking</i>	%	79.4	57.6	93.3	
Packets per Day	N	34	20	14	
<i>1 packet</i>	%	73.5	65	85.7	0.136
<i>2 packets</i>	%	20.6	25	14.3	
<i>More than 2 packets</i>	%	5.9	10	0	
Smoking Years mean (SD)		36.8(13.3)	40.7(13.4)	31.4(11.7)	<0.05
Quit Smoking	N	36	36	0	
<i>Less than 5 years ago</i>	%	11.1	11.1	0	<0.05
<i>5-10 years ago</i>	%	22.2	22.2	0	
<i>More than 10 years ago</i>	%	66.7	66.7	0	
Alcohol consumption	N	340	132	208	
<i>Never</i>	%	86.8	71.2	96.6	<0.05
<i>Occasionally</i>	%	12.1	25.8	3.4	
<i>2-3 times per week</i>	%	0.3	0.8	0	
<i>More than 4 times per week</i>	%	0	0	0	
<i>Every day</i>	%	0.9	2.3	0	
<i>More than 2 times per day</i>	%	0	0	0	

4.3 Prevalence of Frailty by Gender (Table 5)

Of the 340 people under study, one hundred sixty-four (48.2%) were frail, one hundred thirty-one (38.5%) were pre-frail, and forty-five (13.3%) were non-frail (robust).

While the pre-frail condition seemed to be comparable between men and women, other conditions revealed differences. For instance, men were often not frail (24.2% vs. 6.2%), whereas women were more often frail (56.8% vs. 34.8%).

Table 5. Distribution of frailty sum scores according to gender

Frailty assessment	Frailty components	Men			Women		Total	p
		N (%) N=340	N (%) N=132	N (%) N=208	N (%)	N (%)		
Robust	<i>0</i>	45 (13.3%)	32 (24.2%)	13(6.2%)	13.3			
Pre-frail	<i>1</i>	34 (10%)	19 (14.4%)	15 (7.2%)	38.5	<0.05		
	<i>2</i>	97 (28.5%)	35 (26.5%)	62 (29.8%)				
	<i>3</i>	85 (25%)	28 (21.2%)	57 (27.4%)				
Frail	<i>4</i>	63 (18.5%)	14 (10.6%)	49 (23.6%)	48.2			
	<i>5</i>	16 (4.7%)	4 (3%)	12 (5.8%)				

4.4 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Population by Frailty Stages (Table 6)

It is noteworthy that frail people seemed to be older (78.2 ± 7.4 years), more likely to be female (72%), married (51.2%), with children (5.1 ± 2.3 living children), not well educated as compared to pre-frail and non-frail people, never performed any work prior to retirement (57.9%), currently not working (94.5%), are totally dependent on their family members for support (57.3%).

Table 6. Socio-demographic characteristics distributed by frailty stages

VARIABLES	N/%	Total (N=340)	Robust (N=45)	Pre-frail (N=131)	Frail (N=164)	p
Age Mean (SD)		76.3	72.7	75.1	78.2	<0.05
Age Class	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Young Old</i>	%	45.3	68.9	50.4	34.8	<0.05
<i>Middle Old</i>	%	36.8	22.2	35.1	42.1	
<i>Old-Old</i>	%	17.9	8.9	14.5	23.2	
Marital Status	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Single /divorced</i>	%	5.6	4.4	6.1	5.5	<0.05
<i>Married</i>	%	59.7	75.6	64.9	51.2	
<i>Widowed</i>	%	34.7	20.0	29.0	43.3	
Gender	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Male</i>	%	38.9	71.1	41.2	28.0	<0.05
<i>Female</i>	%	61.1	28.9	58.8	72.0	

Table 6 (cont.). Socio-demographic characteristics distributed by frailty stages

Living Conditions	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Living Alone</i>	%	19.1	22.2	16.0	20.7	0.544
<i>Living with others</i>	%	80.9	77.8	84.0	79.3	
No. of living children mean (SD)		4.8 (2.2)	4.3(1.9)	4.5 (2.0)	5.1(2.3)	<0.05
No. of adults in the household mean		1.8 (1.0)	1.9 (1.2)	1.8 (1.1)	1.8(1.0)	0.748
Level of Education	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Illiterate</i>	%	39.1	24.4	29.0	51.2	<0.05
<i>8 years or less of Education (Primary)</i>	%	41.8	46.7	45.8	37.2	
<i>8-12 years of education (Middle)</i>	%	12.6	17.8	16.0	8.5	
<i>12-15 years of education (High)</i>	%	5	8.9	6.1	3.0	
<i>University</i>	%	1.5	2.2	3.1	0	
Currently working	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Yes</i>	%	12.6	31.1	15.3	5.5	<0.05
<i>No</i>	%	87.4	68.9	84.7	94.5	
Prior Occupation	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Without Work (including Household)</i>	%	49.7	22.2	48.9	57.9	<0.05
<i>Agriculture</i>	%	8.8	15.6	6.9	8.5	
<i>Military</i>	%	9.4	24.4	9.2	5.5	
<i>Employee or Manager</i>	%	14.7	22.2	20.6	7.9	
<i>Self-employed Heavy Activity</i>	%	6.8	11.1	4.6	7.3	
<i>Self-employed Light Activity</i>	%	10.6	4.4	9.9	12.8	
Current Monthly Income	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Yes</i>	%	42.9	73.3	45.0	32.9	<0.05
<i>no</i>	%	57.1	26.7	55.0	67.1	
Approximation Monthly Income	N	146	33	59	54	
<i><750,000</i>	%	40.4	36.4	42.4	40.7	0.595
<i>750,000-1,500,000</i>	%	51.4	48.5	52.5	51.9	
<i>1,500,000-3,000,000</i>	%	8.2	15.2	5.1	7.4	
Source of Income	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Current work</i>	%	8.8	17.8	9.9	5.5	<0.05
<i>Stipend</i>	%	26.8	42.2	25.2	23.8	
<i>Using own saving</i>	%	11.8	15.6	13.7	9.1	
<i>More than one source (partially)</i>	%	4.7	2.2	6.2	4.2	
<i>Totally dependent on Family member</i>	%	47.9	22.2	45.0	57.3	

4.5 Geriatric Health Assessment, Co-morbidities, Hospitalization and Lifestyle by Frailty Stages (TABLES 7, 8 and 9)

1. Geriatric health assessment and co-morbidities

Frail participants perceived their health status as being worse than that of others (53%), had significantly more co-morbidities (92.1%), experienced cardiac diseases (52.4%), diabetes (39%), osteoporosis (26.8%) and CVA (12.2%), were prescribed numerous medications (5.1% \pm 3.5), suffered very often from hearing impairment (65.2%), had consumption problems (15.2%), urinary incontinence (47.6%), had fallen during the last year (51.2%), and suffered chronic pain (60.4%). All of the aforementioned differences were statistically significant at $\alpha=0.05$.

Table 7. Geriatric health assessment and co-morbidities by frailty stages

VARIABLES	N/%	Total (N=340)	Robust (N=45)	Pre-frail (N=131)	Frail (N=164)	P
Current Health Status	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Excellent</i>	%	3.2	11.1	3.8	0.6	<0.05
<i>Very Good</i>	%	9.4	20.0	16.0	1.2	
<i>Good</i>	%	50.6	51.1	57.3	45.1	
<i>Fair</i>	%	32.9	17.8	21.4	46.3	
<i>Poor</i>	%	3.8	0	1.5	6.7	
Chronic Disease	%	84.7	73.3	79.4	92.1	<0.05
<i>Cardiac Disease</i>	%	42.9	28.9	35.9	52.4	<0.05
<i>Diabetes</i>	%	32.4	26.7	26	39	<0.05
<i>Joint and Lumbosacral Disease</i>	%	26.8	13.3	26.7	30.5	0.061
<i>Musculoskeletal Disease</i>	%	22.6	8.9	22.1	26.8	<0.05
<i>Lung Disease</i>	%	17.4	8.9	15.3	21.3	0.146
<i>Thyroid Disease</i>	%	12.6	6.7	9.9	16.5	0.103
<i>CVA</i>	%	7.6	2.2	3.8	12.2	<0.05
<i>Cancer</i>	%	2.6	0	2.3	3.7	0.529
<i>Parkinson Disease</i>	%	1.5	0	2.3	1.2	0.695
<i>Dementia</i>	%	1.5	0	0	3	0.097
<i>Kidney Disease</i>	%	4.1	0	5.3	0	0.285
<i>Liver Disease</i>	%	0.9	0	0.8	1.2	
Poly-pharmacy mean (SD)		4.9 (3.2)	2.5(2.5)	3.4 (3.9)	5.1 (3.5)	<0.05
Diet supplement	%	13.8	11.1	15.3	13.4	0.731
Medication with Steroids	%	7.9	6.7	5.3	10.4	0.271
Vision impairment	%	77.6	73.3	79.4	77.4	0.755
Hearing impairment	%	59.1	42.2	57.3	65.2	<0.05
Chronic Pain	%	44.7	15.6	35.1	60.4	<0.05
Pain Scale mean (SD)		6.2 (1.7)	5.4 (2.1)	6.0 (1.6)	6.3 (1.8)	0.494

Table 7 (cont.). Geriatric health assessment and co-morbidities by frailty stages

Pain interpretation	N	152	7	46	99	
<i>Mild pain (1-3)</i>	%	3.9	2.2	1.5	3.0	0.609
<i>Moderate pain (4-6)</i>	%	53.3	6.7	19.8	52.5	
<i>Severe pain (7-10)</i>	%	42.8	6.7	13.7	44.4	
Dental Problems	%	64.1	57.8	59.5	69.5	0.135
Chewing Problems	%	25	17.1	22.1	29.3	0.172
Swallowing Problems	%	4.7	2.2	9.2	15.2	<0.05
Falls during the last year	%	45.3	26.7	44.3	51.2	<0.05
Urinary Incontinence	%	38.2	31.1	29	47.6	<0.05
Stool Incontinence	%	2.9	0	3.1	3.7	0.902
Chronic diarrhea		4.7	2.2	3.8	6.1	0.475

2. Health care and hospitalization

Moreover, frail participants made more clinical visits than their counterparts, and also had higher numbers of hospitalization (1.3 ± 1.7) and length of stay ($3.3 \text{ days} \pm 4.4$).

Table 8. Referring to health care and hospitalization by frailty stages

VARIABLES	N/%	Total (N=340)	Robust (N=45)	Pre-frail (N=131)	Frail (N=164)	p
Dietary consultation	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Yes</i>	%	10.3	8.9	7.6	12.8	0.333
<i>No</i>	%	89.7	91.1	92.4	87.2	
Visits to the Same Physicians	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>No visits</i>	%	3.8	6.7	3.1	3.7	0.186
<i>Yes</i>	%	57.1	68.9	53.4	56.7	
<i>No</i>	%	39.1	24.4	43.5	39.6	
Specialty of referral physician	N	194	31	70	93	
General Practitioner	%	51.5	71.0	51.4	45.2	
Geriatrician	%	6.7	6.5	2.9	9.7	0.174
Cardiologist	%	23.2	12.9	28.6	22.6	
Other	%	18.6	9.7	17.2	22.7	
Number of visits to clinic last year	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Never</i>	%	30	44.4	34.4	22.6	<0.05
<i>1-3 visits</i>	%	47.1	42.2	45.8	49.4	
<i>4 and more visits</i>	%	22.9	13.3	19.8	28.0	

Table 8 (cont.). Referring to health care and hospitalization by frailty stages

Major Barriers for Visits	N	262	39	105	118	
<i>Financial issue</i>	%	10.6	7.7	8.6	13.6	0.335
<i>Transportation issue</i>	%	5.7	7.7	3.8	6.8	
<i>No need to visit a Doctor</i>	%	75.2	76.9	81.9	68.6	
<i>No requested appointment from</i>	%	2.3	2.6	0	4.2	
<i>More than 1 reason</i>	%	6.2	5.2	5.8	6.7	
Number of hospitalizations (SD)		0.9 (1.4)	0.4 (0.8)	0.5 (0.9)	1.3 (1.7)	<0.05
Length of stay in last year (SD)		2.3 (4.7)	1.1 (1.9)	1.6 (5.5)	3.3 (4.4)	<0.05

3. Lifestyle

With respect to the lifestyle of the frail population, physical exercise, smoking, number of packets of cigarettes consumed per day, smoking years and quitting smoking, were found to be non-significant, as compared to that of their counterparts.

Table 9. Lifestyle of the older adult population by frailty stages

VARIABLES	N/%	Total (N=340)	Robust (N=45)	Pre-frail (N=131)	Frail (N=164)	P
Mean of meals per day (SD)		2.3 (0.6)	2.4(0.6)	2.3 (0.5)	2.3(0.6)	0.289
Physical Exercise	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Yes</i>	%	13.2	20	15.3	9.8	0.145
<i>No</i>	%	86.8	80	84.7	90.2	
Smoke	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Ex-smoker</i>	%	10.6	13.3	12.2	8.5	0.423
<i>Current smoker</i>	%	10	15.6	9.2	9.1	
<i>Never smoked</i>	%	79.4	71.1	78.6	82.3	
Packets per Day	N	34	7	12	15	
<i>1 packet</i>	%	73.5	57.1	66.7	86.7	0.209
<i>2 packets</i>	%	20.6	28.6	33.3	6.7	
<i>More than 2 packets</i>	%	5.9	14.3	0	6.7	
Smoking Years mean (SD)		36.8(13.3)	40 (15.2)	32.1(14.2)	39.2(11.5)	0.588
Quit Smoking	N	36	6	16	14	
<i>Less than 5 years ago</i>	%	11.1	0	12.5	14.3	0.949
<i>5-10 years ago</i>	%	22.2	33.3	18.8	21.4	
<i>More than 10 years ago</i>	%	66.7	66.7	68.8	64.3	

Table 9 (cont.). Lifestyle of the older adult population by frailty stages

Alcohol consumption	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Never</i>	%	86.8	71.1	87.0	90.9	<0.05
<i>Occasionally</i>	%	12.1	26.7	10.7	9.1	
<i>2-3 times per week</i>	%	0.3	0	0.8	0	
<i>More than 4 times per week</i>	%	0	0	0	0	
<i>Every day</i>	%	0.9	2.2	1.5	0	
<i>More than 2 times per day</i>	%	0	0	0	0	

4.6 Functional, Cognitive, Psychological and Nutritional status according to the three Frailty Stages (Table 10)

With respect to the functional domain, frail male and female elderly people were very often dependent on others when performing both Basic ADL and Instrumental ADL tasks. While men's dependency was low (6.5% for ADL and 28.3% for IADL), women's dependency was somewhat high (56.8% for both ADL and IADL).

With respect to the cognitive domain, frail elderly people suffered more from cognitive impairment than their pre-frail and non-frail counterparts. Any differences between males and females were found to be negligible.

So far as the psychological domain is concerned, among both genders, frail participants experienced more depression (65.2%) than their pre-frail (40.7% of males and 28.6% of females) and non-frail (12.5% of males and 23.1% of females) counterparts.

With respect to the nutritional status, frail participants were quite often malnourished or at risk of malnutrition. Women were found to be more malnourished than men.

Chi-square tests revealed that frailty was moderately, but significantly, associated with the Activities Daily Living (ADL) score ($\chi^2(4) = 43.367$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .253$), Instrumental ADL score ($\chi^2(4) = 75.740$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .334$), cognitive status (MMSE) ($\chi^2(4) = 31.018$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .214$), GDS score ($\chi^2(2) = 47.976$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .377$), and nutritional status (MNA) ($\chi^2(4) = 52.80$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .284$).

Table 10. Functional, cognitive, psychological and nutritional status according to the three frailty stages

VARIABLES	N/%	Total	Robust		Pre-frail		Frail		p
			(N=45)		(N=131)		(N=164)		
			M	F	M	F	M	F	
Complete Bed Rest (CBR)	N	340	32	13	54	77	46	118	
<i>Yes</i>	%	2.9	0	0	0	0	8.7	5.1	<0.05
<i>No</i>	%	97.1	100	100	100	100	91.3	94.9	
Activity Daily Living (ADL)	N	340	32	13	54	77	46	118	
<i>Very Dependent</i>	%	1.2	0	0	0	0	6.5	0.8	<0.05
<i>Partially Dependent</i>	%	39.4	12.5	7.7	29.6	29.9	50	56.8	
<i>Independent</i>	%	59.4	87.5	92.3	70.4	70.1	43.5	42.4	

Table 10 (cont.). Functional, cognitive, psychological and nutritional status according to the three frailty stages

Instrumental ADL (IADL)	N	340	32	13	54	77	46	118	
<i>Low Function status</i>	%	8.2	0	0	3.7	0	28.3	11	<0.05
<i>Partial Function Status</i>	%	37.9	12.5	0	22.2	35.1	41.3	56.8	
<i>High Function Status</i>	%	53.8	87.5	100	74.1	64.9	30.4	32.2	
Mini Mental State Examination	N	340	32	13	54	77	46	118	
<i>Severe Cognitive Impairment</i>	%	7.4	0	0	1.9	3.9	10.9	13.6	<0.05
<i>Mild Cognitive Impairment</i>	%	19.4	9.4	23.1	9.3	13	23.9	28.8	
<i>No Cognitive Impairment</i>	%	73.2	90.6	76.9	88.9	83.1	65.2	57.6	
Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS)	N	340	32	13	54	77	46	118	
<i>No Depression</i>	%	53.5	87.5	76.9	59.3	71.4	34.8	34.7	<0.05
<i>Depression</i>	%	46.5	12.5	23.1	40.7	28.6	65.2	65.2	
Mini Nutritional Assessment	N	328	32	13	53	76	42	112	
<i>Malnourished</i>	%	22.3	0	23.1	11.3	14.5	21.4	39.3	<0.05
<i>At risk of malnutrition</i>	%	37.8	18.8	30.8	39.6	32.8	47.6	42.9	
<i>Normal Nutritional Status</i>	%	39.9	81.2	46.2	49.1	52.6	31.0	17.8	

4.7 Frailty Stages and Frailty Criteria (Table 11)

When comparing each of the frailty criteria under study, frail participants experienced higher percentages of frailty than their pre-frail counterparts.

Chi-square tests revealed that frailty was *moderately associated*, but significantly, with the weight loss criterion ($\chi^2(2) = 43.448$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .370$), *relatively strongly associated* with exhaustion ($\chi^2(2) = 1.018E2$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .547$) and physical activity ($\chi^2(2) = 1.141E2$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .579$), *strongly associated* with the speed test criterion ($\chi^2(2) = 1.527E2$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .670$), and the grip strength criterion ($\chi^2(2) = 1.473E2$, $p = .000$, Cramer's $V = .667$).

Table 11. Frailty stages distributed by frailty criteria

VARIABLES	N/%	Total (N=340)	Robust (N=45)	Pre-frail (N=131)	Frail (N=164)	p
Weight loss criteria	N	317	45	127	145	
<i>Frail</i>	%	22.1	0	11.8	37.9	<0.05
<i>Non-frail</i>	%	77.9	100	88.2	62.1	
Exhaustion criteria	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Frail</i>	%	35.6	0	13.7	62.8	<0.05
<i>Non-frail</i>	%	64.4	100	86.3	37.2	
Speed test criteria	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Frail</i>	%	68.2	0	59.5	93.9	<0.05
<i>Non-frail</i>	%	31.8	100	40.5	6.1	

Table 11 (cont.). Frailty stages distributed by frailty criteria

Grip strength criteria	N	331	45	128	158	
<i>Frail</i>	%	68.9	0	62.5	93.7	<0.05
<i>Non-frail</i>	%	31.1	100	37.5	6.3	
Physical activity criteria	N	340	45	131	164	
<i>Frail</i>	%	47.4	0	28.2	75.6	<0.05
<i>Non-frail</i>	%	52.6	100	71.8	24.4	

5. DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to describe the levels of physical, psychological and social functioning according to the three frailty stages of Fried's Phenotype method, and to identify the prevalence of frailty among community-dwelling older people in a rural area of Lebanon using a cross-sectional study. The results obtained demonstrated consistent differences for all three domains between the non-frail, pre-frail and frail older people.

Frail people had poorer scores than their pre-frail and non-frail counterparts, and older people that were pre-frail had intermediate scores that came between the scores of frail and non-frail older people.

The socio-demographic characteristics of the population studied seemed to be similar to the characteristics of Lebanese elderly people that were reported by Sibai et al.⁽⁵⁷⁾ Females were more predominant in the sample than males, which is similar to International ratio differences between older females and males.⁽¹³⁶⁾

In the sample group studied, around two-thirds of the older people were married. Married men were twice as common as women. On the other hand, the number of widowed women was higher than widowed men; this data is similar to that reported by PAPFAM 2004.⁽¹⁰⁾ This may translate into better support for men in their later years, assistance in their daily activities, nutritional support and companionship.

Another important finding of the study is the fact that older women, like in the PAPFAM survey, were significantly more often illiterate, more often financially dependent on their family members, and more often living alone than men.

Interestingly, 28% of older men aged 65 years and over continued to work after the official age of retirement, while only 2.9% of older women did so; these percentages seem to be very close to those reported in the PAPFAM survey.⁽¹⁰⁾ Further, the older people in the study often suffered from visual and hearing impairment, which may also impair their social interaction. These percentages were greatly higher than those reported by PAPFAM. Differences may be slightly exaggerated due to self-reporting of vision and hearing impairment without referring to any assessment tests.

Moreover, among females, chronic diseases, poor nutritional status, functional disability in basic ADL and IADL, depression and cognitive impairment were common and significantly more frequent than in men. Other authors reported similar findings in international and regional settings. Gender and rural differences were described by Kabir et al. in a cross-sectional study conducted in rural and urban areas in Bangladesh.⁽¹³⁷⁾ 80% of older women in both regions reported having more health problems than older men (only 42%). They also reported difficulties with ADL. Another study conducted by Barry et al.⁽¹³⁸⁾ showed that women were more likely to develop depression than men.

Likewise, women in the sample population also seemed to be more disadvantaged, according to objective indicators such as number of drugs taken, number of hospitalizations and length of stay, and number of falls during the last year. However; women considered their health as being fair or poor more so than men, and also more often reported chronic pain. These findings match results of studies about SHR and pain conducted by Chemaitelly et al. in underprivileged communities in Beirut⁽¹³⁹⁾ and by Wrangler et al⁽¹⁴⁰⁾ respectively.

A high prevalence of frailty (48.2%) was documented for the studied sample. A high prevalence of frailty was found in the sample of community-dwelling older citizens of the Shouf area in Lebanon; this prevalence is slightly higher than that reported by Boulos et al. in a Lebanese study concerning malnutrition (36.4%)⁽¹¹⁸⁾, but was about the same as that found in a similar study conducted in the United Arab Emirates by Al Kuwaiti et al. (47%).⁽³⁶⁾

While different studies reported disparities between rural and urban areas,⁽⁴⁵⁾ a cross-sectional study conducted by Sabah et al. reported that major differences between urban and rural settings decreased in severity due to the internal and external displacement of the Lebanese population and the rapid evolution of communication services in Lebanon.⁽¹⁴¹⁾ However, the rural population may be more vulnerable because of limited access to health care services, and lower socio economic status; these factors have been shown to be associated with frailty.⁽¹⁴²⁾

Eggimann et al., in a large-scale study conducted among community-dwelling elderly people living in ten different countries in Europe, which yielded estimates of frailty using Fried's Phenotype method⁽³³⁾, showed that the proportion of frailty or pre-frailty was higher in Southern than in Northern Europe. For instance, Spain showed an estimate of 27.3%, Italy 23%, Germany 12.1% and The Netherlands 11.3%; these estimates in proportions are much lower than those reported in our study.

Another study conducted by Alvarado et al. concerning frailty and health conditions among older men and women in Latin America reported a percentage of frailty that varied from 30% to 42.6% between cities where frailty was 26.7%, 39.5% and 42.6% in Bridgetown, Mexico and Santiago, respectively.⁽³⁵⁾

The variation between studies is probably due to several reasons, such as the use of different measurement methods to determine each frailty criterion,^(37,143) differences between socio-economic status of older people and political conditions in different countries, differences in life styles, such as exercise and nutrition.

Several studies reported that frailty is significantly associated with multiple factors, such as advancing age, female gender, being unmarried,⁽³⁶⁾ living alone or among subjects who reported being lonely,⁽¹⁴³⁾ or older people with a low level of education.⁽¹⁴⁴⁾ Similarly, in this study, frailty among Lebanese elderly people living in rural areas was associated with aging, female gender, being widowed, as well as being illiterate or having had only 8 years of education. On the other hand, living alone did not pan out as a risk factor. A number of studies have shown that living in a rural area is associated with greater co-residence and a lower prevalence of living alone among elderly people.⁽¹⁴⁵⁾ Sibai et al., in a study of living arrangements of married women in Lebanon, reported that co-residence was more frequent with unmarried than married children, with a greater likelihood of co-residency with male married children.⁽¹⁴⁾ Noteworthy is that members of the same family in Lebanon live together, if not in the same household, then in the same environment, where older family members play an essential role with respect to family responsibilities.

Regarding self-reported health status, it was found that fair/poor health was more commonly reported by the female than the male participants. In addition, a significant association was observed with frailty. These findings are similar to those of Pichardo et al, who published results of a cross-sectional study conducted among 927 community-dwelling elderly people aged 70 and older in Mexico.⁽¹⁴⁶⁾

The measurement scores for the physical domain were most favorable for the non-frail elderly people, and worst for the frail people. Pre-frail participants in our study suffered from a higher number of chronic diseases than their non-frail counterparts. The number of chronic diseases was even higher among the frail people. These results are comparable to those reported by Fried and his colleagues'.⁽²⁷⁾

In Fried's study, cancer was the only chronic condition that was not significantly different between the frailty stages. In our study, frailty was associated with chronic disease including cardiovascular, diabetes mellitus, musculoskeletal disease and CVA. There were non-significant associations between stages of frailty and other diseases. We suggest that this non-significance was due to the self-reporting of diseases by participants. In a country such as Lebanon, people may tend to misunderstand some of their medical situations. Sometimes self-health reporting seems to be inaccurate.

Frailty was associated with falls ($p < 0.05$) and hospitalization ($p < 0.05$), whereby women reported more falls and more hospitalizations than men. This result is similar to a prospective cohort study conducted among British community-dwelling elderly people and similar to pooled results from studies in a systematic review and Meta-analysis.⁽¹⁴⁷⁾ Frailty was a significant and independent predictor of short-term future falls and hospitalization respectively.⁽¹⁴⁸⁾

While a systematic review by Kojima et al. yielded that smoking can be seen as a predictor of a worsening frailty status in a community-dwelling population and that smoking cessation may potentially be beneficial for preventing or reversing frailty, smoking and quitting smoking was not significantly associated with frailty. This may be due to the small share of the population that reported to be smokers.⁽¹⁴⁹⁾

Our findings demonstrated that physical frailty is closely tied to a significant worsening of psychosocial factors. Specifically, it was found that depressive symptoms are progressively higher in robust, pre-frail, and frail groups. We also showed a significant interaction effect of ADL, demonstrating that the performance of ADL differs depending on the combination of frailty stages. Frail subjects showed a lower level of ADL compared to non-frail individuals. Our results are consistent with those obtained by Anna M. et al., in a cross-sectional study conducted in Italy.⁽¹⁵⁰⁾ Buigues et al. reported that depression and frailty occur in a significant proportion of frail elderly individuals,⁽¹⁵¹⁾ which was also shown in our study.

Since both frailty and cognitive impairment are increasingly prevalent with advancing age, several studies examined the association between frailty status and cognitive impairment. A longitudinal cohort study of 840 community-dwelling elderly people using Fried's Phenotype and MMSE reported that among the oldest people, frailty status was significantly associated with cognitive impairment.⁽¹⁵²⁾ This result is similar to that reported by our study, whereby frailty stages were statistically significantly associated with cognitive impairment.

In the same context, malnutrition is significantly associated with frailty in this study. Our data confirm the similar findings reported by Boulos et al. concerning the relationship between frailty and the nutritional status of community-dwelling elderly people.⁽¹¹⁸⁾

Finally, the association between the three frailty stages and the different criteria of Fried's Phenotype was moderate. Frailty was associated with weight loss, moderate associated with physical activity and exhaustion, but strongly associated with gait speed test and hand grip strength. These results are similar to those reported by Kannegieter et al. in a cross-sectional study, where frail participants needed significant more time to complete the Gait Speed test, and had significant lower handgrip strength.⁽¹⁵³⁾

5.1 Study difficulties and limitations

This study has several strengths, including the large representative sample, the high similarity of socio-demographics with national statistics reported by PAFAM in 2004⁽¹⁰⁾ and with a high response rate, meaning that our results can be generalized for elderly people living in other rural areas of Lebanon. In fact, few studies focused on the specific characteristics of this population and literature shows conflicting results.^(45,46) Unfortunately, in Lebanon, no comparison is possible as similar data from urban settings is not available.

Moreover, to our knowledge, this is the first study reporting prevalence of frailty and associated factors in elderly Lebanese community-dwellers based on the Phenotype method (golden standard criteria) of Fried et al.⁽²⁷⁾ Also, data collection for assessment of functional, nutritional, cognitive and psychological status was based on widely used and well validated instruments.

Several limitations have to be considered in this survey. Firstly, its cross-sectional design, which does not allow the drawing of causal relationships. Secondly, even though our random sample can be considered to be representative for the rural elderly people in the Shouf district, we could not do any weighting to provide estimates of the prevalence of frailty for the whole rural population of Lebanon, due to the lack of population data in rural areas. Moreover, a part of our questionnaire was based on self-reported information, which may be affected by memory and information bias due to educational disparities (response and recall bias).

Finally, several instruments were initially developed for western cultures, which may not be culturally sensitive to Lebanon. For example, the MNA has not been validated previously for the population of Lebanon. Thus, it may be of great importance to undergo validation studies of this important screening tool, as well as of several other specific geriatric assessment tools that have not yet been validated among the population of Lebanon.

5.2 Implications

All of the results across all domains showed the same trend, indicating more preferable scores for non-frail compared to frail older people, with intermediate scores for the pre-frail people.

The five Fried frailty criteria could help healthcare professionals to efficiently identify and treat frail elderly people, and provide indications of problems in other domains. In subsequent assessment of problems and risks, one requires a multidimensional approach; as our data has shown that often problems in various health domains co-exist. Further longitudinal research is needed to obtain a better view of which factors predict the negative consequences of frailty and what interventions could be undertaken to reverse it if possible.

6. CONCLUSION

The cross-sectional study is relevant since it expands conceptual knowledge of frailty and identifies the prevalence of frailty among elderly individuals in rural areas of Lebanon in a representative sample of the population. Thus, the present study sought to provide data on frailty, and to determine risk factors for the development of frailty, so that we can prevent its occurrence, to develop plans to address it; and to set the stage for future research projects.

Based on our findings, it was possible to conclude that the prevalence of frailty in the elderly population in the community studied is 48.2% and that frailty was associated with chronic diseases, with functional, psychological and cognitive status, as well as a higher use of healthcare resources. The study results reinforce the need for education about frailty, its consequences and treatment

interventions, since it is a predictor of many adverse health outcomes such as falls, disability, and mortality.

Awareness of this problem will lead to the creation and implementation of timely preventive and adaptive measures that can delay or minimize this syndrome in the elderly population. Further, it is important for healthcare practitioners working with elderly people to recognize frailty as a risk factor for imminent adverse outcomes, even in those who appear to be aging well.

Healthcare systems in developing countries need to pay attention to the frailty syndrome, since it impacts healthcare services, morbidity and mortality. Indeed, future research is important, because many questions concerning frailty remain unanswered, such as the development of more accurate user-friendly tools to predict adverse outcomes, interventions to prevent developing it from one stage to another. Interventions must be confirmed and extended.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

While frailty and its respective stages is a rather new concept of research in the Arab region, and because ignoring frailty syndrome has a negative impact on aging society, the health care system has a high cost on health-related complications, we recommend these issues to be addressed.

In Lebanon, because of the lack of statistics and accurate data, computing the real population of Lebanon is a dire activity. Therefore, a consensus should be held, so that accurate data on the number of Lebanese people and Syrian refugees is available, with respect to demographics and social characteristics of these populations.

While the majority of elderly people screened in this study, reported a lack of regularly follow-up by a healthcare professional, and some of them did not make any medical visit during the last year at all, we recommend that, in order to improve their health care management, a patient health record booklet is created that allows healthcare professionals to document progression of their patients' health conditions, vaccinations, regular geriatric assessment, recurrent hospitalization and treatment care plan. Such a booklet may enhance the traceability of health information by different healthcare professionals, especially seeing that a significantly large group of elderly people did not refer to the same physician. Another solution would be the introduction of uniform computerized health records.

While several Geriatric scales are used in Arab countries for assessing the health status of their elderly population, which were initially developed in developed countries, are validated in the English language, some have been translated into Arabic language, but they need to be validated then in the Lebanese society in different settings to ensure their reliability and specificity for general use.

While our study showed that the majority of elderly people were followed by General Practitioners for primary health care, many were unaware of their health status; many were depressed and frail and yet did not have any treatment plan to rectify the situation. We recommend that GPs and other healthcare providers be educated about frailty, including its diagnosis, factors and treatment.

Since several studies have shown that there is an interrelationship between frailty, social and psychological conditions and while Fried phenotype measure only the physical frailty of older adults. In the Arab region where some countries experience political turmoil such as war, terrorism, and other unrest, there is a need to create an appropriate measurement tool for frailty, should take the above changes and their circumstances. We suggest that these situations increase the likelihood of frailty development among vulnerable elderly people and strategies to prevent its development should be undertaken.

Since frailty has an enormous impact on acute hospital care and has been shown to be a more effective predictor of mortality, we recommend the development and implementation of special programs that aim to identify frailty stages, and the implementation of interventions to prevent its progression and to reverse it. Such programs should include education of the public and health sector about frailty. In addition, programs directed at improving nutrition, exercise and mood may today prevent it.

Since frailty is considered as a new concept in research of health care providers, it is expected that elders may misunderstand the alert symptoms which diagnosed it. Although a crucial need to enhance the level of education and knowledge of this population to ensure a better outcome seem to be pivotal.

When the frailty syndrome considered to be a reversible health condition between different frailty stages when some interventions are applied by older adults, a crucial need to identify and implement specific programs which focus on needs of frail citizens and interventions to prevent frailty syndrome and the negative transition between stages (from robust and pre-frail to frail) and impacts on society.

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